

The Life of the Kaibarta's in the story *Ekhon Nodir Mrityu* (Death of a River)-An Analytical Study

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Introduction to the Subject:

The *Ronga Jiya* poet Mahim Bora is the author of the story '*Ekhon Nodir Mrityu*'. The story was written in 1972. The story describes the problems faced by the Kaibarta community along the Kalang River in the 1970s as a result of unplanned government schemes. The paper is prepared to analyse the social life of the Kaibarta community that lived beside the Kalang River. As the river stagnates, inertia descends into the life of the Kaibarta community. The story '*Ekhon Nodir Mrityu*' has been chosen as the subject of the paper in order to create a sense of reality of the Kaibarta community in disaster as the riverine community is the victim of inaction of the upper classes.

Methodology of the study:

Analytical method has been used to study the lower class Kaibarta people in the story '*Ekhon Nodir Mrityu*'.

Review of Literature:

There are many previous discussions about the post-war storyteller Mahim Bora's story '*Ekhon Nodir Mrityu*', such as—

The ecosystem and symbolic consonants reflected in the story is discussed in the book "*Boroniya Byaktittot Mahim Bora*" (2018) by Kalpana Hazarika Gayan.

Kalpana Hazarika Gayan paints the picture of riverine society in her book '*Prajanmar Dusokut Mahim Bora*' (2018). Discussion of the story '*Ekhon Nodir Mrityu*' can be seen in two books of the writer.

1.0 Concept And Definition of Marginality in Literature:

In order to conceptualize marginality in the primary sphere, two aspects must be mentioned: a) the concept of marginalization as a place, and b) the concept of marginalization in the social sphere.

But when we raise the question of what marginality is in literature, we must take both the concepts of place and society as resources. In other words, marginality in literature can only be spoken of through the opposite medium. The concept of marginality is not new. It has been observed in the field of socio-literature since ancient times. The gap between the upper and lower castes is spontaneous. The lower classes have been exploited and neglected by the upper classes since the past. Marginal literature is literature that includes people living in marginalized areas and socially neglected. This literature reflects the grievances, society and culture, problems and struggles of the lower classes for equality. Marginal literature is composed only by the marginal lower class people.

If we want to define marginal literature, it can be said that it is the literature composed by neglected, exploited, peasant people who raise their social issues and problems and how they have to struggle for their rights after long oppression.

The opposite concept of marginality in literature has been seen in the story '*Ekhon Nodir Mrityu*' by Mahim Bora which is chosen as the subject of the paper. The story is about the lower class community resided on the bank of the Kalang River in Nagaon district of central Assam, located in the eastern part of India. In parallel, the study of the social problems of the oppressed, neglected lower classes in a society in which the concept of marginality is also clearly reflected in the life of the Kaibarta society. The story describes about the riverine Kaibarta community of Kalang who become nearly death with the exploitation as similar to the dead river Kalang for the short sighted scheme of government. The concept of marginal literature is clearly reflected in the detailed analysis of the story.

2.0 The Kaibarta community in the story '*Ekhon Nodir Mrityu*':

The story '*Ekhon Nodir Mrityu*' by Mahim Bora is about the post-war riverine society on the bank of Kalang river. The storyteller Mahim Bora portrays the Kaibarta community formed centring the Kalang River flowing through Nagaon district through the household of Dhaneswar. The story reflects all the social, economic and cultural aspects of the riverine people on the bank of Kalang. Bora also mentions the Kalang river as the main source of livelihood of the riverine people in the story along with other occupations such as the agricultural, sailor and skipper occupations. They were mainly engaged in fishing.

"Nothing else is needed, not even the talks of our father's day, I could able to earn my bread by fishing only in three attempt with cast net along with gill and push net in this Kalang river not so long ago. At that time, people could able to earn his bread without any difficulty only by fishing."

If there is water in the flowing Kalang, it means there is fish. The farmers of the Kalang river's bank are wealthy with crops because of the fertile soil left by flood every year. This Kalang is also the driving force behind crop production. The storyteller expresses this through the dialogue of a character in the story named *Bhadre*, in the following way—

“Shallow lands, earlier fields of this area were covered with liveliness and crop production disappeared altogether as soon as the Kalang dries up.”

Many Kaibartas earned their living by sailing on the river. But in the story, the storyteller's concerns of mind have been expressed frequently. The riverine society of Kalang river dies in the heart of death Kalang. The says in the language of the story by observing the dried river in the following way—

“What will the people of the river banks of this Kalang earn their living from today? The people with some land will cultivate, but what will the people do who depend on fishing for earning their life?”

The livelihood of the Kaibarta community around the Kalang is possible including Kalang river. The storyteller portrays the poor livelihood of the riverine people due to the changes in the Kalang river and the cessation of its flow.

The storyteller not only portrays the livelihood of the Kaibartas, but also their domestic environment, socio-cultural and economic conditions. The main character of the story is Dhaneshwar, who is introduced as a fisherman. Dhaneshwar and his household paint a vibrant picture of the daily life of the riverine people. The familiar picture of domestic life of Kaibarta community, such as—Dhaneshwar gets up early and goes for fishing, interaction of Dhaneshwar and his wife and his inner anger to beat her up, arrange water for bathing, serving food and waiting for husband, selling fish and sometimes fiddlehead fern from house to house, they are even pessimistic about living in poverty in a family full of children and brothers. Everyone in the riverine people has self-confidence that they want to benefit themselves, not by deceiving others. Even after seeing people become victims of deception of the rich in the city of Nagaon and making money through illegal means, they chose not to compromise their individuality, honesty which indicates their simplicity of mind. The storyteller has given a dialogue through the character Dhaneshwar to express the picture of social unity—

“They also go to work together to light fires in the fields, to pick up grains and lentils in the alluvial islands or sand banks. They also go to the village to sell fish in groups of two or three. Therefore you don't have to tell them to sit down when they visit your home.”

Though there is a touch of modernity but the storyteller shows the folk beliefs and superstitions of the Kaibarta people in the story. The social life of these riverine people is full of dignity. Along with the unnatural death of the Kalang river which was the enlivening force of Kaibarta and the conventional flow of life came to a halt with the death of the river. In the post-independence period, the government adopted several schemes to advance Indian society. The implementation of government schemes, the construction of dams on both banks of

the Kalang River and the construction of bridges over the Kalang River brought disaster to the riverine community. The storyteller explains this somewhere:

“Is there such a fool country? Do you kill a living river in a country? Did the son of damned person take independence for this? If you stand in the water for half an hour, the whole body will be shaken.”

With the death of the living river, the concept of Kaibarta society and culture ceased to exist who lived beside the river Kalang. Water hyacinth made all these a dense forest. Does it kill *Jhao* (Tamarix Indica)? Didn't the government kill a nation along with this?

Because of the political conspiracy, engagement of foreigners along with big leaders in the construction of road etc. benefitted the higher and royal class of people. As a result, it brought darkness to the lives of the riverine people. The river Kalang died due to the short-sighted plans of the government. Through the character Dhaneshwar, the storyteller portrays the exploitation over the lower class poor people. The influence of modernism devastated the life journey of the Kaibarta people. The storyteller tells us that when the river died, some people moved up to the north bank of Brahmaputra.

The storyteller Mahim Bora discusses all the aspects such as the decline in the desire for work-culture and folk culture among the younger generation of the riverine people with the death of the river in such a way as to put an elephant in a small pitcher. The storyteller says about the aversion of the new generation to work:

“Why don't you look at the boys of our village today? Which boy is better at studying or at work? They roam around wearing pants, they are good for nothing. Why our village, what about the other village boys? They play cards and dice in tea shops and walks around in the morning and evening. They are nowhere, nor in cultivation, nor trade, nor education, nor even at advocate, lawyer job with a high salary.”

In the story, the storyteller discusses broadly about the livelihood, domestic environment and the existence of a community that was washed away by the dying river Kalang due to political turmoil. The storyteller covers all aspects like drops of water make ocean in the story about the lifestyle and struggles of the lower class Kaibartas who grew up around the Kalang river.

2.0 Conclusion: “*Ekhon Nodir Mrittyu*” is one of Bora's stories. The story covers the fishing community on the banks of the Kalang River in the post-independence period. The story is about the misery and suffering of the Kaibartas brought about by the implementation of public welfare schemes undertaken by the government of Assam during the era of 'Rainbow'. The story deals with realistic issues such as the destruction of ethnic life in the frenzy of unplanned schemes of government, the abolition of local occupations in the name of mechanical progress, the reluctance of the next generation to pursue education and the tendency to avoid work.

The story is about the cause and ways of changing direction in the lifestyle of the riverine community that emerged around the Kalang river which flows through Nagaon district. The storyteller beautifully presents the changes in the lifestyle of the riverine community from a literary perspective. There is a clear sense of marginal consciousness in two lines of the story.

“The Kalang river lies still in front of their eyes, stagnant with premature widowhood and premature old age.”

With the passage of time, the life, literature and culture have disappeared from the margins of the lower classes. The storyteller has therefore given a literary form by thoroughly studying the Kaibarta society.

Context Source:

1. Lilavati Shaikia Bora, *The Flow of Assamese Short Stories*, p. 110–111
- 2, *Assamese Short Stories Flow*, p. 112 mentioned, *Assamese Short Story B Prabah*, p. 111 . 111
- 3Cited, p. 312 . 312
- 4*ibid.*, p. 110
- 5*ibid.*, p. 111 . 111
- 6*ibid.*, p. 118 ‘
- 7*ibid.*, p. 118

Bibliography:

- Shaikia Bora, Lilavati, *asomiya sutigolpor probah*, Fourth Edition, Guwahati University Press, Guwahati, 2018
- Hajbika Gayan, Kalpana, *projonmor duskut mohim bora*, First Edition, Krantikal Prakashan, Nagaon,2018
- Hajnika Gayan, Kalpana, *boroniya byakttitot mohim bora*, first published,2019